

Meiotic chromosomes of male green leafhoppers (GLH)

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We studied the meiotic chromosomes of GLH *Nephotettix virescens*. Newly emerged, insectary-reared GLH males were fixed in Carnoy's fluid for 24 h. Later, their testes were macerated on glass slides with a drop of 2% lacto-aceto-orcein and 45% acetic acid. Chromosome examinations showed that GLH spermatogonia divided mitotically and spermatocytal processes followed the conventional reduc-

1. Chromosomes of male *N. virescens* at diakinesis showing $2n=15$ (7IIA+XO). The sex chromosome is indicated by an arrow. Magnification, 1500X (oil immersion). IRRI, 1984.

2. *N. virescens* pachytene chromosomes comprising autosomes, chromosome with nucleolar organizing region (NOR), and sex chromosome and idiogram showing the relative mean lengths. Sex chromosome is indicated by an arrow. Magnification, 1500X (oil immersion). IRRI, 1984.

tional-equational meiotic divisions. The primary spermatocytes at diakinesis (Fig. 1) had 7 bivalent autosomes and a univalent X-chromosome making the genomic complement $2n=15$ (7IIA + XO).

At pachytene (Fig. 2), relative mean chromosome length was 0.074-0.189. The sex chromosome measured 0.083 and the autosome with the nucleolar organizing region (NOR) had a relative mean length of 0.153. These chromosomes condensed maximally during premetaphase into

dumbbells of bivalents measuring as follows: 4, 3, 3, 2.5, 2.5, 2.5, 1.9, and 1. The sex chromosome measured 1μ while the chromosome with NOR measured 3μ .

The insemination potential of male GLH as determined by the mean meiotic index was approximated to be 0.84.

Spontaneous chromosomal aberrations in individual GLH included 0.77% hypoploidy or reduction in chromosome number and 0.47% agmatoploidy or increase in number. □

Host plants of rice leafhopper (LF)

Marasmia patnalis Bradley

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Simultaneous damage to rice leaves by two LF species, *Marasmia patnalis* Bradley and *Chaphalocrocis medinalis* Guenée, was observed on the IRRI experimental farm from Oct 1983 to Mar 1984. *C. medinalis* commonly feeds on alternative hosts, but no information is available on the ability of *M. patnalis* to survive rice-free periods on alternative hosts. We tested *M. patnalis* survival on nine rice-field weeds (see table) in a no-choice trial

Weeds tested as host plants to the LF *M. patnalis*,^a IRRI, 1984.

Family, plant ^b	Survival from 1st instar to pupa ^c (%)	Remarks on feeding of larvae
Poaceae (Gramineae)		
<i>Leersia hexandra</i>	48 a	Severe scraping
<i>Leptochloa chinensis</i>	14 b	High scraping
<i>Echinochloa glabrescens</i>	4 bc	Low scraping
<i>Echinochloa colona</i>	0 c	Scraping was observed, but larvae did not live to pupate.
Cyperaceae		
<i>Cyperus difformis</i>	2 c	Two adjacent leaves near the tip of the inflorescence were folded.

^aTen replications/plant species, 5 larvae/plant. ^bIdentified by R. T. Lubigan, IRRI. ^cMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different (P = 0.05) by Duncan's multiple range test. There was no survival on *Fimbristylis littoralis*, *Monochoria vaginalis*, *Ipomoea aquatica*, and *Sphenoclea zeylanica*.